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NLR family gene methylation correlates with survival in breast cancer.

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We studied mechanisms that specifically and significantly influence survival in human cancer by comparing DNA methylation globally in patient tumors based on total number of days (overall survival). We identified numerous instances of differential methylation of NLR family genes which was quantitatively significant indicating a family-specific property that is associated with patient survival. We suggest NLR family function interaction with survival results from a broad association between senescence program and NLR receptors through interferon.